

ISic1084

I.Sicily inscription 1084

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

prope sepulcrum Theronis

Coordinates**Current Location**

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492713

EDR 136235

EDCS 39102242

PHI 140567

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0265 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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